

1 **Supplemental information for: A codon model for**
2 **associating phenotypic traits with altered selective**
3 **patterns of sequence evolution**

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22 Running title: Coding sequence - phenotype integrated model

23 Keywords: Evolutionary selection; intensification, relaxation, genotype-phenotype; γ -

24 proteobacteria; SEMG2;

25 **Supplementary Text**

26 **Supplementary Text 1**

27 **The expected history approximation**

28 The likelihood of the sequence data is computed while conditioning on the history of
29 trait transitions. Here we provide more details on how this computation is performed.

30 Let H denote a random variable representing the history of character state
31 transitions along the phylogeny T , and let h be a single possible realization of H . We
32 define a new tree, T_h , where each point of a trait transition defines an internal node
33 with a single descendent lineage.

34

35 The expected history, $E(h)$, is a single history that summarizes a set of possible trait
36 histories. The expected history is constructed by computing the expected time spent
37 in each state in each branch over the entire set of histories. These can be computed
38 in two alternative approaches: a sampling-based approach, in which these values
39 are obtained as the average over a finite sample of N stochastic mappings (as done
40 in Mayrose and Otto 2011; Levy Karin et al. 2017), or in an analytic approach, which
41 considers all possible trait histories and uses the rewards method of Minin and
42 Suchard (2008). As described below, in our implementation we followed the more
43 accurate analytic computation.

44

45 First, the ancestral states are determined based on the posterior probabilities of
46 character states at internal nodes, as obtained from the character model and data
47 (Nielsen 2002). Let $f_{n,i}$ be the posterior probability of observing character state i in
48 ancestral node n . Then, the state assignment to node n in $E(h)$ is $argmax_i(f_{n,i})$.

49 Next, the expected times spent in character states '0' and '1' and in each branch b
50 along T , termed here $E(t_0^b)$ and $E(t_1^b)$, are computed. Specifically, we compute for
51 each branch in the phylogeny the total evolutionary reward for the expected times
52 spent in the two character states. This value is computed based on a fixed set of
53 rewards $\{\omega_0, \omega_1\}$ for character states '0' and '1', respectively (equations 1.4-2.12 in
54 Minin and Suchard 2008). As such, setting ω_0 to 1 and ω_1 to 0 yields a total
55 evolutionary reward value that is equal to $E(t_0^b)$. Similarly, $E(t_1^b)$ can be obtained by
56 setting ω_0 to 0 and ω_1 to 1.

57

58 Once the above expectations are computed, the location of state transition along
59 each branch (if there was one) has to be resolved. Consider a branch, b , whose
60 parent node is assigned with state '1' and child node with state '0' (or vice versa) and
61 the expected time spent in state '1' is $E(t_1^b)$. In this case, we heuristically define the
62 expected history of b to contain a single transition, whose location is $E(t_1^b)$ time units
63 away from the parent node (although in practice it could be any odd number of
64 transitions). Alternatively, in case both parent and child nodes are assigned with the
65 same state, there must be either zero (if $E(t_0^b)$ or $E(t_1^b)$ is equal 0) or an even
66 number of transitions along the respective branch (if neither $E(t_0^b)$ nor $E(t_1^b)$ is equal
67 0). In the latter case, the time spent in the shared state is heuristically divided such
68 that there are two transitions along the corresponding branch (from the shared state,
69 to the alternative state, and then back to the shared state). The locations of state
70 transitions are determined based on the posterior probabilities of the shared state at
71 the two terminal nodes. Specifically, let b be a branch of length t in which the
72 inferred state at both parent and child nodes is '0', the expected time spent in state

73 '0' is $E(t_0^b)$, and the expected time spent in state '1' is $t - E(t_0^b)$. Then, b is divided to
 74 three segments, such that the middle segment (in red below) is assigned to state '1'
 75 and the two terminal segments (in black) to state '0'. The lengths of the segments
 76 are determined as follows:

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85 where $f_{parent,0}$ and $f_{child,0}$ are the posterior probabilities of being in state '0' at the
 86 parent and child nodes, respectively.

87 While the heuristic choice to incorporate a minimal number of character transitions in
 88 history does not necessarily reflect reality, it appears to have little effect on the
 89 accuracy of the approximated trait evolution (see Fig. 1 in supplementary text 2).

90

91 **Supplementary Text 2**

92 **Adequacy of the approximated likelihood function**

93 The full likelihood function of TraitRELAX (Equation 6 in the main text) integrates
94 over all possible character histories. Since this integration is not feasible, the
95 computation is approximated by a set of N sampled stochastic mappings (Equation 9
96 in the main text denoted here the exhaustive approximation). The accuracy of this
97 approximation increases with the number of sampled histories, N , but becomes
98 prohibitively long even for a modest value of N , given the large size of the codon rate
99 matrix. When examining its performance, we chose $N = 1,000$ as a balanced tradeoff
100 of accuracy/running time. Alternatively, this computation is approximated by a single
101 expected history (see Supplementary Text 1 and Equation 10 in the main text) which
102 is computed analytically (denoted here as the expected history approximation). While
103 this heuristic computation yields markedly lower running times, it could result in
104 inaccurate likelihood computations. Thus, we examined the adequacy of these
105 approximations by measuring the difference in the computed log-likelihood values
106 compared to that obtained using the true, simulated, history.

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108 As shown in Supplementary text 2, Fig. 1, the log-likelihoods obtained using the
109 expected history approximation were consistently more similar to those of the true
110 history as compared to those obtained using the exhaustive approximation.

111 Moreover, the variance of the log-likelihood was greater when using the exhaustive
112 approximation than when using the expected history approximation. Additionally, the
113 expected history approximation is deterministic and thus yields a stable likelihood
114 computation, unlike the exhaustive approximation which is susceptible to the
115 stochasticity of the sampled mappings. Together, this suggests that the expected

116 history approximation is both closer to the true history as well as more robust and we
117 therefore opted to use this approximation in all analyses conducted in this study.

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120 **Supplementary Text 2, Figure 1. Comparison of the log-likelihoods obtained**

121 **using the exhaustive and expected history approximations. The distribution of**

122 *the differences between the log-likelihood values obtain using the true (simulated)*

123 *history and those obtained using either the expected history approximation (green)*

124 *and the exhaustive approximation (blue). The distributions are computed for 50*

125 *simulations of trees with 32 taxa, 300 codon positions and $k = 0.5$ with character*

126 *transition rate of (a) $\mu = 1$, (b) $\mu = 2$, (c) $\mu = 4$ (d) $\mu = 8$, and (e) $\mu = 16$*

127 *corresponding the mean number of simulated transitions (a) 1.96, (b) 4.28, (c) 9.08,*

128 *(d) 16.14, and (e) 29.58.*

129 **Supplementary Text 3**

130 **Sequence likelihood computation approach**

131 The sequence model of TraitRELAX consists of three site categories that model the
132 different selective regimes that operate on the codon positions using three ω
133 parameters ($\omega_0 > 1$, $\omega_1 \approx 1$, $\omega_2 > 1$ for purifying, neutral and positive selection) and
134 two branch categories (*BG* and *FG* corresponding to segments evolving under state
135 '0' and '1', respectively) that model changes in the intensity of selection in the *FG*
136 branches relative with the *BG* branches using a selection intensity parameter k . As
137 such, each selective regime c is modeled in the *BG* branches by the value of the
138 respective ω_c parameter and by the value ω_c^k in the *FG* branches.

139

140 An important, yet overlooked, consideration when computing the likelihood of a
141 branch-site codon model concerns with the nature of shifts between site categories
142 (in this case, selective regimes) across branches. Consider three adjacent branches,
143 such that b_1 and b_2 are the descendant lineages of b_3 . There are three ways to
144 compute the sequence likelihood when moving across branches. The first option,
145 which we followed in the implementation of TraitRELAX, restricts the site category in
146 all branches to be the same, whether they belong to the same branch category or
147 not. Thus, if a position evolved under ω_0 in b_3 , it would evolve under ω_0 also in b_1
148 and b_2 . Notably, because each branch category has its own value of ω for each site
149 category (e.g., ω_0 of the *FG* category is set to ω_0 of the *BG* category raised to the
150 power of k) the site can still experience a change in the magnitude of selective
151 pressure upon transitioning from b_3 to b_2 , but not when transitioning between two
152 adjacent branches that belong to the same branch category.

153

154 In a second alternative, the site category assigned to each position may vary
155 between adjacent branches only if the ancestral one is assigned to the *FG* category
156 and its descendent is assigned to the *BG* category. In this case, a site evolving under
157 ω_0 in b_1 , may evolve under any ω category in b_2 . A possible shortcoming of this
158 approach is that it allows for more combinations of site-categories assignments in
159 certain branch partitions. Specifically, if a transition between branch categories
160 occurs in an internal branch (e.g., b_3 is assigned as *FG* while b_1 and b_2 as *BG*), the
161 constraint on the ω assignment for the two descendant branches is relaxed, such
162 that a site may evolve under ω_0 in b_3 , ω_1 in b_2 , and ω_2 in b_1 . On the other hand, if the
163 transition between branch categories occurs in an external branch (e.g., b_1 is
164 assigned as *FG* while b_3 and b_2 as *BG*), the constraint on the ω assignments is
165 relaxed only for the single external branch (b_1). This issue could bias multiple testing
166 procedures that iteratively assign a single branch to the *FG* category and test for the
167 presence of positive selection on that branch (e.g., Anisimova and Yang 2007) as it
168 might favor certain partitions of branches that allow for more combinations of
169 assignments to site-categories. Because this approach is the one most commonly
170 used by the community (for example, in the popular software package PAML; Yang
171 1997), further research is needed to explore its behavior.

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173 In a third and most permissive approach, which is used for example by Wertheim et
174 al. (2015) and implemented in the HyPhy package, the site category assigned to
175 each position may vary across all branches, regardless of their assigned branch
176 category. This approach allows for rapid shifts in site categories that are not
177 necessarily realistic, such as shifts from purifying to positive selection along very
178 short branches, and can thus lead to a high rate of false positives (Kosakovsky Pond

179 and Frost 2005). In addition, this approach could lead to confounding effects
180 between parameters in the model (e.g., between the selection intensity parameter k
181 and the ω parameters; see Discussion in the main text).

182 **Supplementary Text 4**

183 **Running time analysis**

184 The running time of TraitRELAX was examined when using the analytic
185 approximation, which proved sufficiently accurate. However, the running time of
186 TraitRELAX may vary based on the chosen approximation approach. To assess the
187 effect of the chosen approximation on the running time, we measured the mean
188 running time of a single likelihood computation given each approximation approach
189 (Supplementary text 4, table 1). As expected, the results show robustness of the
190 single expected history based approximation to the number of sampled stochastic
191 mappings, while the running time of the exhaustive approximation increases by a
192 magnitude of 13.46 upon an increase of the number of mappings by 10.

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194 ***Supplementary text 4, Table 1: Comparison of the running time at a single likelihood computation on a Linux machine with a single CPU. For each computation type, the mean running time over 100 executions are shown, based on simulations with 32 taxa, 300 sequence positions and $k=0.5$***

Mode of approximation	Number of mappings	Running time^a
Exhaustive	100	5.997 (3.257)
	1000	80.75 (21.20)
Sample based expected history	100	0.124 (0.072)
	1000	0.177 (0.057)
Analytic expected history		0.165 (0.067)

^aMean running time in minutes. The standard deviation is shown in parentheses.

195 **Supplementary Figures**

196 **Supplementary Figure 1**

197

198 **Sensitivity and FPR assessment for various data sizes.**

199 The percent of simulated datasets in which the null hypothesis was rejected by
200 TraitRELAX using the LRT when the LR threshold was determined according to
201 parametric bootstrapping (top row; a-c) or approximated using the χ^2 distribution
202 (bottom row; d-f) with a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$. Results are shown for
203 different number of taxa: 16 (panels a and d), 32 (b and e), and 64 (c and f)
204 (simulation scenario 1, Table 1 in the main text). The y axis indicates the false
205 positive rate in the case of $k = 1$, and the statistical power for all other k values.

206 **Supplementary Figure 2**

207

208 **Accuracy of inferring k as a function of data sizes.** (a,c,e) The distribution of the
 209 inferred k parameter by TraitRELAX and (b,d,f) its average inference error for
 210 simulations with different number of species: 16 (panels a-b), 32 (panels c-d) and 64
 211 (panels e-f) (simulation scenario 1, Table 1 in the main text). The horizontal lines
 212 within the box plots indicate the median inferred values and the red dots indicate the
 213 simulated (true) values of k . The error is measured as $|\log(\hat{k}) - \log(k)|$ to account
 214 for the exponential effect of k on the ω values of branch category 1.

215 **Supplementary Figure 3**

216

217 **The distribution of the inferred k and ω parameters for simulations with**
218 **various values of k .** For each simulated k value, the box plots are ordered from left
219 to right for the inference of: ω_0 , ω_1 , ω_2 , and k . The horizontal lines within the box plots
220 indicate the median inferred values and the black dots indicate the simulated (true)
221 values. All simulations were conducted with 32 taxa and 600 codon positions
222 (simulation scenario 1, Table 1 in the main text).

223 **Supplementary Figure 4**

224

225 **Sensitivity assessment of the branch-site model RELAX.** The percent of

226 replicates for which RELAX rejected the null model is shown for simulations with (a)

227 32 taxa and different numbers of codon positions, and (b) 300 codon positions and

228 different numbers of taxa, given partitions based on the maximum parsimony

229 solution (simulation scenario 1, Table 1 in the main text). Rejection of the null

230 hypothesis was determined using the χ_1^2 approximation to the LRT as recommended

231 in Wertheim et al. (2015). In all cases, the cutoff for rejection was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. In

232 comparison to TraitRELAX, the sensitivity of RELAX was lower under all simulation

233 conditions (see Fig. 2 in the main text).

234 **Supplementary Figure 5**

235

236 **Comparison of parameter estimation accuracy between TraitRELAX and**

237 **RELAX.** The distribution of the inferred values of k by (a) TraitRELAX and (b)

238 RELAX when given partitions based on the maximum parsimony solution are shown

239 for simulations with increasing number of taxa and 600 positions (simulation scenario

240 1, Table 1 in the main text). The horizontal lines within the box plots indicate the

241 median inferred values and the simulated values are shown in dashed lines. (c) The

242 mean error of the inferred values of k by TraitRELAX (solid lines) and RELAX given

243 the maximum parsimony partition (dashed lines) is shown for simulations with 32

244 taxa, 600 positions, $\pi_0 = 0.5$, $k = 0.5$ and increasing values of μ : 1, 2, 4, 8, 16

245 (simulation scenario 2, Table 1 in the main text), corresponding to the following

246 mean number of transitions: 2.21, 4.01, 7.88, 16.3, 31.93 and (d) with increasing

247 values of π_0 (for a fixed value of $\mu = 8$, $k = 0.5$) (simulation scenario 3, Table 1 in the

248 main text). The error is measured as $|\log(\hat{k}) - \log(k)|$ to account for the exponential
249 effect of k on the ω values of branch category 1.

250 **Supplementary Table 1. Inference of TraitRELAX on the 68 γ -proteobacteria**
251 **house-keeping genes.** Genes for which a significant result was obtained following
252 the false discovery rate (FDR) correction for multiple testing (Benjamini and
253 Hochberg 1995) at $\alpha = 0.05$ are marked with an asterisk. The p -values were
254 computed based on the parametric bootstrapping procedure and then adjusted using
255 the FDR procedure, yielding the q -values.

Gene	Null log likelihood	Alternative log likelihood	q -value	Inferred model parameters					
				ω_0	ω_1	ω_2	p_0	p_1	k
relaxed genes									
rpsI	-7058.83	-7020.19	0.02*	0.00	0.10	1.00	0.50	0.44	0.78
yeaZ	-23683.94	-23668.87	0.02*	0.03	0.21	1.00	0.45	0.44	0.84
pgi	-41974.07	-41951.28	0.02*	0.01	0.14	1.00	0.62	0.32	0.84
ybeY	-13392.69	-13384.74	0.02*	0.02	0.18	1.00	0.57	0.35	0.87
asnS	-36378.68	-36360.03	0.02*	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.54	0.40	0.88
mnmA	-29626.72	-29614.07	0.02*	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.53	0.43	0.91
holB	-39217.16	-39210.18	0.06	0.04	0.24	1.00	0.40	0.54	0.91
argS	-48722.57	-48704.89	0.02*	0.02	0.15	1.00	0.59	0.36	0.91
rpsQ	-4830.86	-4829.68	0.77	0.01	0.13	1.00	0.44	0.53	0.91
ftsY	-42810.06	-42800.02	0.02*	0.02	0.14	1.00	0.35	0.31	0.91
fold	-23296.47	-23290.92	0.06	0.01	0.14	1.00	0.58	0.38	0.92
pheT	-72828.14	-72809.01	0.02*	0.03	0.15	1.00	0.59	0.37	0.92
Orn	-14477.09	-14474.10	0.15	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.51	0.42	0.94
rplR	-6463.44	-6462.78	0.81	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.41	0.52	0.94
gidA	-48523.88	-48515.69	0.02*	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.57	0.39	0.94
mraW	-27320.87	-27316.95	0.17	0.01	0.12	1.00	0.53	0.44	0.95
glyS	-58718.79	-58711.50	0.06	0.02	0.12	1.00	0.44	0.50	0.95
rplV	-5196.22	-5195.46	0.82	0.02	0.19	1.00	0.82	0.17	0.95
obgE	-30463.72	-30460.65	0.18	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.51	0.45	0.95
prfA	-28119.78	-28117.17	0.21	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.50	0.47	0.95
aspS	-47605.40	-47601.81	0.32	0.02	0.13	1.00	0.49	0.43	0.95
Frr	-14880.83	-14879.66	0.72	0.03	0.15	1.00	0.60	0.38	0.96
yggX	-6552.94	-6552.34	0.72	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.50	0.48	0.96
engA	-41097.47	-41093.58	0.21	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.56	0.40	0.96
trmE	-38986.82	-38983.78	0.29	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.52	0.41	0.96
dnaN	-30511.33	-30508.33	0.33	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.64	0.32	0.96
Ffh	-33607.23	-33604.40	0.18	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.67	0.31	0.97
rbfA	-11245.17	-11244.33	0.72	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.37	0.52	0.97
Pnp	-49921.49	-49919.78	0.81	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.56	0.36	0.97
infB	-65673.58	-65671.73	0.58	0.02	0.12	1.00	0.49	0.45	0.98
rplJ	-9987.03	-9986.93	0.97	0.04	0.17	1.16	0.63	0.34	0.98
yidC	-43555.73	-43555.35	0.98	0.03	0.20	1.00	0.56	0.38	0.98

rpoA	-14884.91	-14884.56	0.88	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.65	0.34	1.00
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intensified genes

Pth	-17673.78	-17673.35	0.83	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.43	0.53	1.00
rplX	-5745.55	-5745.53	0.99	0.02	0.13	1.00	0.52	0.46	1.00
nusA	-34326.92	-34326.82	0.98	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.65	0.34	1.01
ftsH	-42017.26	-42016.70	0.90	0.01	0.11	1.00	0.71	0.26	1.02
yrbA	-7244.76	-7244.54	0.88	0.03	0.12	999.00	0.38	0.62	1.02
rpmA	-4779.06	-4778.99	0.97	0.02	0.18	1.00	0.77	0.21	1.02
rplA	-14992.97	-14992.61	0.88	0.02	0.13	1.00	0.60	0.38	1.02
rpsG	-7517.22	-7516.85	0.90	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.71	0.26	1.03
pyrH	-16848.44	-16847.17	0.58	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.68	0.31	1.03
rpsF	-7439.89	-7439.63	0.93	0.04	0.22	1.00	0.49	0.43	1.04
rpsA	-30783.29	-30781.23	0.96	0.02	0.14	1.00	0.64	0.35	1.04
aceE	-58653.32	-58648.72	0.58	0.02	0.16	1.00	0.57	0.41	1.05
Tsf	-21220.15	-21218.33	0.54	0.03	0.17	1.00	0.47	0.51	1.05
rplQ	-6480.60	-6479.79	0.67	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.51	0.39	1.05
rplO	-8749.55	-8748.57	0.82	0.01	0.12	1.00	0.43	0.54	1.06
rplT	-6179.76	-6178.22	0.44	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.62	0.36	1.06
secY	-25094.28	-25083.52	0.02*	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.64	0.36	1.06
rplK	-7959.80	-7958.73	0.72	0.02	0.15	1.00	0.68	0.31	1.06
rplI	-10623.93	-10622.72	0.64	0.03	0.15	1.00	0.39	0.57	1.06
rplE	-8438.27	-8437.15	0.72	0.02	0.17	1.00	0.64	0.34	1.07
rpsR	-3131.34	-3130.83	0.82	0.01	0.13	1.00	0.64	0.33	1.08
rho	-21447.11	-21440.78	0.02*	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.84	0.16	1.08
rplM	-7428.74	-7427.16	0.44	0.02	0.17	1.00	0.62	0.35	1.09
rpsB	-13719.86	-13716.33	0.27	0.02	0.14	1.00	0.55	0.39	1.09
rpsP	-5636.77	-5635.06	0.44	0.02	0.13	1.00	0.43	0.48	1.10
rplP	-6088.36	-6085.79	0.22	0.02	0.14	2.79	0.65	0.35	1.11
rplS	-6084.20	-6079.72	0.18	0.02	0.10	1.00	0.53	0.43	1.11
rplB	-13727.93	-13721.89	0.06	0.01	0.14	1.00	0.60	0.37	1.13
rpsM	-6351.64	-6349.60	0.33	0.02	0.23	1.00	0.57	0.38	1.13
infA	-3065.84	-3062.17	0.08	0.01	0.10	28.43	0.71	0.28	1.14
rpoB	-73750.02	-73701.12	0.02*	0.01	0.17	1.00	0.66	0.32	1.16
rplN	-4879.27	-4875.46	0.06	0.01	0.13	1.00	0.64	0.33	1.21
rpoC	-78720.19	-78645.42	0.02*	0.01	0.19	1.00	0.69	0.28	1.21
rpsN	-5546.14	-5539.38	0.04*	0.02	0.17	1.00	0.51	0.47	1.23
rpsJ	-3591.13	-3578.45	0.02*	0.01	0.10	1.00	0.78	0.21	1.36